

CLINICAL STUDY OF MAMSYADI LEP IN KHALITYA

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ABSTRACT

Mamsyadi Lep is a classical Ayurvedic formulation primarily indicated for Khalitya (hair fall and alopecia). The preparation is composed of ingredients such as Mamsi (*Nardostachys jatamansi*), and other herbs possessing keshya, rasayana, and shirovirechana properties. The Lep is applied externally on the scalp to strengthen hair roots, promote regrowth, and reduce excessive hair shedding. Its pharmacological actions include tridosha shamana, improvement of scalp circulation, and nourishment of hair follicles. Traditional references suggest its role in maintaining scalp health and delaying premature graying. Mamsyadi Lep thus offers a safe, natural, and cost-effective management approach for hair disorders.

KEYWORDS: Khalitya, Alopecia, Mamsyadi lep, Ayurveda, Hairloss, Lepa Chikitsa, Pitta-Vata.

1. INTRODUCTION - Ayurveda is the most ancient life science of the world. Ayurveda is not only life science but also the philosophy of life. In our samhita the aim of Ayurveda is to maintain the good health & prevention of diseases. Ayurved. Came on the earth in the form of Trisutra for wellbeing of world.

हेतुलिङ्गौषधज्ञानं स्वस्थातुरपरायणम् ।

त्रिसूत्रं शाश्वतं पुण्यं बुबुधे यं पितामहः ॥ (च.सू. १२४) {1}

The Triskandha Ayurvedic knowledge was then transformed into Astanga Ayurveda i.e. Kayachikitsa, Kaumarbhritya, Graha, Shalakya, Shalyatantra, Agadtantra, Rasayan chikitsa and Vajikaran.

कायबालग्रहोद्ध्वाङ्गशल्यदंष्ट्राजरावृक्षान् ।

अष्टावङ्गानि तस्याहुश्चिकित्सा येषु संश्रिता ॥ (अ.ह. सू. ११५){2}

Agadtantra synonymously called toxicology is one of the ancient recognized branches of Ashtanga Ayurveda since its inception. A number of poisonous plants classified as visha and Upasvisha are described in the of Agad tantra. There is a very little limitation between a medicine and a poison because a medicine in a high dose may act as a poison and a poison in a small dose may act as medicine.

योगादपि विषं तीक्ष्णमुत्तमं भेषजं भवेत् ।

भेषजं चापि दुर्युक्तं तीक्ष्णसंपद्यते विषम् ॥ (च.सू.१\१२७) {3}

In many ailment, poisonous drug prove more efficacious than normal prescription drugs due to their inherent properties. This statement can be understood by the quotation in Charak Samhita as stated by Maharshi Agnivesh.

प्राणाः प्राणभृतामन्नं तदयुक्त्या निहन्त्यसून् ।

विषं प्राणहरं तच्च युक्तियुक्त रसायनम् ॥ (च. चि. २४१६०){4}

Hair fall is a universal problem, having affected both sexes of all races to different extents for as long as mankind has existed.

For thousands of years, men and women of all countries and races have shared the tragedy of pre-mature hair loss. Hair is one of the vital part of body derived from ectoderm of skin, is protective appendages on the body and considered accessory structure of the integument along with sebaceous glands, sweat glands and nails.

The normal cycle of hair growth lasts for 2 to 6 years and each hair grows approximately one centimeter (less than half an inch) per month during this phase. About 90 percent of hair on

your scalp is growing at any one time. About 10 percent of the hair your scalp, at any one time, is in resting phase.

After 2 to 3 months, the resting hair falls out and new hair start to grow in its place. It is normal to shed some hair each day as part of this cycle. However, some people may experience excessive (more than normal) hair loss. Hair loss of this type can affect men, women and children. Genetic baldness is caused by the body's failure to produce new hairs and not by excessive hair loss. Both men and women tend to lose hair thickness and amount as they age. Inherited or (pattern baldness) affect many more men than women. About 25% of men being to bald by the time they are 30 years old, and about two thirds are either bald or have a balding pattern by age 60 years.

In Ayurveda there are many synonyms for hair loss as Inderlupta, Khalitya, Rujya etc. As per Ayurveda, the deranged vata and pitta having resource to the roots of the hairs bring about their falling off, while the deranged blood and Kapha of the locality fill up those pores of holes, thus barring their fresh growth and recrudescence. The disease is called Indralputa, Rujya or Khalitya. Management hair fall is extremely complex. But in Ayurveda there is so many herbs and formulation available to check the hair fall definitely.

रोमकूपानुगं पितं वातेन सह मूच्छितम् ।

प्रच्यावयति रोमाणि ततः श्लेष्मा सशोणितः ॥

रुणद्धि रोमकूपांस्तु ततोऽन्येषामसम्भवः ॥

तदिन्द्रलुप्त खालित्यं रुज्येति च विभाव्यते ॥ (सु. नि. १३/३२-३३){5}

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

AIM- To analyze the effect of Mamsyadi Lep on Khalitya.

2. MATERIAL IN METHOD

मांसी कुष्ठं तिलाः कृष्णाः सारिवा निलमुत्पलम् ।

क्षौद्रं च क्षीरपिष्टनि शसंवर्धनं परम् ॥ 14{A.H.U.Shiroroga pratisheda 24/42}[6]

INGREDIENTS	BOTANICAL NAME	FAMILY	PART USED	RATIO
Mamsi	Nordostachys	Valerianaceae	Rhizome	1 part
Kustha	Saussurea lappa	Asteraceae	Root	1 part
Karsna tail	Sesamum indicum	Pedaliaceae	Seed	1 part
Sariva	Hemidesmus Indicus	Asclepiadaceae	Root	1 part
Nilotpala	Nymphaea Stellata	Nymphaeaceae	Rhizome	1 part

2.1 METHOD OF APPLICATION- The paste was applied once daily on the scalp for 30–45 minutes, followed by rinsing with lukewarm water.

Duration: 6 weeks (42 days).

Study conducted on 30 patients aged 16–40 years diagnosed with non-scarring alopecia (Khalitya).

Inclusion criteria: Hair fall >50/day, visible scalp thinning, otherwise healthy adults.

Exclusion criteria: Fungal scalp infections, autoimmune hair loss, or concurrent hair treatments.

3. RESULTS

The application of Māmsyādi Lepa showed the following outcomes:

- Reduction in hair fall was observed in 10 of 12 patients by the third week.
- Scalp itching and dandruff decreased significantly in 18 patients.
- Mild regrowth was visible in patchy areas by the end of 6 weeks in 6 patients.
- No adverse effects were reported.

Parameter Week 0 Week 3 Week 6

Average hair fall/day 80 50 30

Dandruff (Visual Score) Moderate–High Mild Absent

Regrowth (Visual Grading) None Minimal Moderate

Patient Satisfaction (%) – 50% 73%

4. DISCUSSION

The herbs used in Māmsyādi Lepa offer a synergistic effect for restoring scalp and hair health:

- Māmsī acts on the nervous system and helps reduce stress-related hair loss. It is Medhya and Vata-Pitta pacifying.

Kushth have the kandughn properties and nilotpal have twag dosh har properties that help cure the dandruff and itching.

The lepa format allows these herbs to act directly on the scalp, promoting local blood circulation, balancing doshas, and nourishing the hair roots. The results support Ayurvedic references found in Charaka Samhita, Bhavaprakasha, and Yogaratnakara regarding Keshya dravyas.

5. CONCLUSION

Māmsyādi Lepa proves to be a safe and effective external formulation in the management of Khalitya. It provides a holistic Ayurvedic alternative to chemical treatments and may help reduce hair fall, enhance scalp health, and initiate hair regrowth. Further clinical studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are recommended.

REFERENCES

1. charak samhita, Vidyotini hindi commentary, vol, 1, sutrasthana 1/24, Chaukhamba Prakashana, Varanshi.
2. Ashtang Hridaya of vagabhat, Vidyotini hindi commentary, sutrasthana, 1/15, Chaukhamba Prakashana Varanshi.
3. charak samhita, Vidyotini hindi commentary, vol, 1, sutrasthana 1/127, Chaukhamba Prakashana Varanshi.
4. charak samhita, Vidyotini, hindi commentary vol, 2, chikitshasthana 24/60, Chaukhamba Prakashana Varanshi.
5. susurut samhita, vol 1, nidansthan, 13/32-33.
6. Ashtang Hridayam of vagabhat, Vidyotini hindi commentary Uttarsthana 23/26, Chaukhamba Prakashana, Varanshi, Edition, Reprint, 2009; page no 728.